

Pulse Geomagnetic Perspective ASAR RO

Analysis of the magnetosphere's frequency to support inertial navigation.

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Strategic Void Beyond GNSS dependency

In modern operations and autonomous exploration,
satellite signal is vulnerable. High-resolution magnetometry
represents the only absolute alternative.

The Advantage of 20 - 200 Hz: Micro-Dynamics

High Temporal Resolution

The majority of standard observatories operate at 1 Hz. The ASAR system records at 20 - 200 Hz, capturing the micro-structure of the magnetic field and the invisible precursors to conventional sensors.

- Granular analysis of the magnetosphere
- Detection of Pc3/Pc4 cavity waves
- Reduction of phase error through dense sampling

Navigation in GNSS-Denied Environments

By using ASAR phase analysis, inertial systems can maintain course in areas with heavy jamming or loss of satellite signal.

Our algorithm distinguishes between physical rotation and magnetic torsion, eliminating the “ghost” errors that mislead conventional drones.

3D Detrended Fluctuation Analysis of Magnetic Field Attractor MF-DFA

Introduction

Analyzing 24-hour intervals of acquisition data from high-resolution IMU inertial sensors in the framework of independent seismic and geophysical observation and monitoring activities, a Hurst correlation of 0.92 was observed in the daily files, which determined the multidimensional reconstruction of the data and subsequent complex analyses.

Study analysis

We built a 3D attractor model for the analysis of the magnetic-angular correlation, isolating only the inclinometer and magnetometer axes from the IMU data, the gyroscope being intentionally immobilized and the thermal drift left free for safety correlation.

Inertial recordings have been carried out since 2021 and up to now on selected intervals and also for constant recording over long periods of time at a frequency of 20Hz but also on weekly intervals of 200 Hz. These geophysical data acquisitions were carried out in 3 locations in Romania: the northeastern border with Ukraine, the Vrancea seismic zone, and Surlari in the south of the country. The data were verified by comparison with the same IMU model but connected to various other models of data acquisition systems.

The result of the attractor analyses reveals an interesting three-dimensional map and very useful in multiple spheres of activity starting from the forecast of major solar magnetic events to Magnetic Field Anomaly Navigation (MAGNAV) and Quantum Shielding. In parallel with the attractor imaging, other analysis methods were performed for various tasks presented at the end of this observation summary.

Observations

Analysis results

In the next images you can see the "topographic" results of the 3D attractor, these two images represent the analysis of data from two different locations at different resolutions, Fig 1. 200 Hz and Fig 2. 1000 Hz made with a rent magnetometer.

3D Detrended Fluctuation Analysis of Magnetic Field Attractor MFDFA

Figure 1

3D Detrended Fluctuation Analysis of Magnetic Field Attractor MF DFA

Figure 2

It is observed from the images below the weaker magnetic compression in the northeastern region.

High compression of the southern magnetic field

You can be our collaborator to continue the research on the following geophysical observations:

- Magnetic Hour: secular analysis of magnetic drift allows visualization and forecasting of the "magnetic hour", thus for the southern region the printed values are noted:

ASAR SYSTEM: SECULAR MAGNETIC TORSION ANALYSIS

PERIOD:2026-02-20 -> 2026-04-20

INTERVAL:59 days

OLD MAGNETIC TIME: 20.2839 h

NEW MAGNETIC TIME:20.2206 h

TOTAL ADVANCE:23.9367 hours

DAILY RATE: 0.405706 hours/day

MONTHLY RATE:

12.1712 hours/month

Observations of the magnetic hours correlate with the activity of geomagnetic storms but also with technological noise and the analysis tools built allow tracking this anchor in real-time and over longer time intervals.

- Multiple realities related to space-time symmetry that collide in a singularity and a hidden chronometer of the spiral progression observed at a 1000 Hz analysis by digital microscopy inside the geometric model in the attractor possible related to the fundamental spin evolution. The anomalies of the space-time symmetry represent the area of overlap of the environmental entropy, more precisely the convergence foundation of the two or more states of the environment reflected by the geomagnetic geometry. In the image below, it was possible to isolate these anomalies and highlight them by subtraction in the attractor model.

- Seismic and Geophysic Monitor

- Testing the coherence of environmental entropy

Highlighting temporary spatial anomalies

Predictive Intelligence Space Weather on Earth

ASAR RO not only records data, but also detects magnetospheric shocks before they impact electronic systems.

Application Pillars

Resilience

Navigation systems resilient to electromagnetic spoofing and jamming.

Aero-Spatial

Magnetic field-based attitude sensors for sub-orbital missions.

Infrastructure

Critical monitoring of power grids against geomagnetically induced currents (GIC).

ASAR vs. Standard Magnetometry

Feature	Standard Observation	ASAR RO Precision
Sampling Rate	1 Hz	20 Hz (Ultra-High Resolution)
Precursor Detection	Limited / Reactive	Predictive (Volatility Analysis)
Phase Analysis	Simple Vector	3D Holographic (Torsional)
Navigation Applicability	Limited (Static)	Tactical (Dynamic / Inertial)

*The future of navigation is not found in the stars,
but in deciphering the invisible rhythm of the planet.*

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